

Data Dictionary: Medsys AI Pre-clinical Trial Dataset

This document provides a description of each variable in the dataset generated from the Medsys AI pre-clinical trial.

Variable Name	Description
doc_id	A unique identifier for each consultation record stored in the trial's database.
user_id	A unique identifier for the participating physician within the Medsys AI system.
patient_id	A unique identifier assigned to the virtual patient for a specific consultation.
interaction_id	A unique identifier for the specific physician-patient interaction record.
trial_arm	The randomized group to which the consultation was assigned. Possible values are control (physician worked unassisted) or intervention (physician received Medsys AI assistance).
case_id	An identifier corresponding to the original clinical vignette used to program the virtual patient for the consultation.
gold_standard	The correct, pre-defined diagnosis for the clinical vignette, which serves as the ground truth for evaluating diagnostic accuracy.
medsys_diagnostic_HIGH	The diagnostic suggestion generated by Medsys AI with the highest assessed probability or confidence.
medsys_diagnostic_MEDIUM	The diagnostic suggestion generated by Medsys AI with a medium assessed

	probability or confidence. Note: In some cases, more than one medium-probability diagnosis may be provided.
medsys_diagnostic_LOW	The diagnostic suggestion generated by Medsys AI with the lowest assessed probability or confidence.
user_diagnostic_1	The primary diagnosis submitted by the physician, representing what they considered the most likely diagnosis.
user_diagnostic_2	The secondary diagnosis submitted by the physician, considered less likely than user_diagnostic_1.
user_diagnostic_3	The tertiary diagnosis submitted by the physician, considered the least likely of the three.
elapsed_time	The total duration of the consultation in seconds, measured from the moment the physician started the recording until the final diagnoses were submitted.
created_at	The timestamp indicating when the consultation was completed and the physician saved the diagnoses.
recorded_conversation	A text transcript of the entire conversation between the physician and the virtual patient. Note: All conversations were conducted in Spanish.
medsys_external_evaluation	The consensus evaluation from the three blinded adjudicators regarding the accuracy of the Medsys AI's suggestions. A correct diagnosis by the AI is indicated by one of the following codes: M1: The gold_standard matches medsys_diagnostic_HIGH. M2: The gold_standard matches a medsys_diagnostic_MEDIUM. M3: The

	gold_standard matches medsys_diagnostic_LOW. "Missed" value indicates an incorrect diagnosis.
user_external_evaluation	The consensus evaluation from the three blinded adjudicators regarding the accuracy of the physician's submitted diagnoses. A correct diagnosis by the physician is indicated by one of the following codes: D1: The gold_standard matches user_diagnostic_1. D2: The gold_standard matches user_diagnostic_2. D3: The gold_standard matches user_diagnostic_3. "Missed" value indicates an incorrect diagnosis.
concordance_AI_and_doctor	A boolean flag (True/False) indicating whether the physician's primary diagnosis (user_diagnostic_1) was the same as the AI's primary suggestion. This variable is used in the safety analysis to assess automation bias.